

STUDIES IN THE PASSIVITY OF CHROMIUM. PART I. THE ELECTRODIC BEHAVIOUR OF CHROMIUM AND ITS BEARING ON THE PASSIVITY OF THE METAL

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Chromium electrodes of different types show different behaviour in buffer solutions originally free from the metal ions. Massive and powdered electrodes set potentials which are more positive than those prepared by electrodeposition. The potentials set after heating the electrodes in hydrogen and subsequently in high vacuum are less positive than those set in aerated solutions.

The E_0' values obtained in air by extrapolating the linear portions of the p_H -potential plots amount to -400 mv as compared with -30 to -100 mv out of contact with air, corresponding thus to a difference of one volt and 400 mv respectively from the thermodynamic E_0' value of the Cr/Cr₂O₃ system which amounts to -570 mv. This positive shift is attributed to an oxygen overvoltage effect contributing much to the passivity of the metal.

The passivity of chromium and other similar metals have long been the point of several discussions. Numerous theories have been advanced to explain the cause of passivation and the nature of the passive state. One theory assumes the formation of a thin protective film of oxide which needs only to be a single molecule thick (Evans, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1020). The difficulty that known oxides do not usually have the necessary resistance to acids is overcome by assuming that oxygen is adsorbed in a kind of Langmuir film or as oxygen doublets (Meunier, *Bull. soc. chim. Belg.*, 1927, 36, 435; Tourky *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 750; 1949, 1297); or that it forms a kind of alloy with the metal which occupies definite positions in the space lattice (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1919, 103, 107). Others consider the oxide to be unstable but becomes stabilised on the metal (Bennet and Burnham, *Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1916, 29, 217). Evidence as to the cause of passivity may be gained from a study of the electrode behaviour of chromium metal under a variety of conditions in solutions initially free from the metal ions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Electrodes.—The chromium electrodes used in this investigation are of the following types:

A: Stick electrodes $1\frac{1}{2}$ cm. in length and 7 mm. in diameter, prepared by the mechanical shaping of Kahlbaum metal lumps. Electrical contact was maintained by a copper wire soldered to one end of the electrode. The latter was fixed to a glass tubing with a rubber tubing, previously treated with boiling dilute HCl.

B: Powdered electrodes obtained by grinding the metal lumps. The sample that passed through a sieve of 1600 mesh/cm² was treated with a solution of KOH, followed by HCl, then boiling redistilled water and finally with alcohol and ether before drying in a desiccator. The powder was placed in small glass cups surrounding short tipped platinum wires sealed into glass tubings.

C: Electrodeposited electrodes, prepared by deposition from a chromic acid bath on a copper substrate, following the procedure recommended by Field and Duddly ("Electroplating: A Survey of Modern Practice", 6th. Ed., p. 379, 1951). The copper base was obtained by electrodeposition on platinum sheets (1×1 cm.) sealed to glass tubings through a platinum wire. Electrical contact in case of the powdered and electrodeposited electrodes was maintained through mercury and copper wires introduced into the glass tubings.

Solutions.—The buffer solutions used for the electrode potential measurements were the Clark-Lubs and Ringer buffers of the p_{H} values 1 to 10, 11 and 12 (cf. Britton, "Hydrogen Ions", Vol I, Chapman and Hall, London, 1942, pp. 301–311). Potassium chloride solution was prepared by dissolving the Analar product in twice distilled water. Cells and apparatus were essentially the same as used by Tourky *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

The measurements were carried out both in air and after the electrodes had been subjected alternately to the action of hydrogen and to high vacuum at 400° (type C) or 1000° (types A and B) using the electrode jackets shown in Fig. 1. Jacket 1 A is made of soda glass and is adapted for use with the electrodeposited electrodes. The jackets b and c are made of silica glass and are suited for use with the two other types.

DISCUSSION

Behaviour of Chromium Electrodes in Air

Electrodes of type A set up potentials which tend in general to assume more positive values with time (curves a, b and c, Fig. 2). In solutions of p_H values 1 to 6 the potentials tend after prolonged immersion to assume less positive values and are found to vary

FIG. 2

S, P and E denote respectively stick, powder and electrodeposited Cr.

to a certain extent with p_H , which is not the case in the alkaline buffers (curves c and c', Fig. 3). The potentials set at p_H 1 lie in the vicinity of the hydrogen electrode potential, whereas those set at p_H 2 to 12 lie on the positive side of the hydrogen electrode slope. This behaviour is possibly due to the disturbing effect of the chloride ions on the oxide film responsible for the passivity of the metal, rendering it permeable to most reagents (Isgarischeff and Obrutcheva; *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1923, 29, 428).

Contrary to these observations, the potentials set by the same type of electrodes during the neutralisation of the universal buffer mixture of Britton and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1456) vary in an excellent manner with p_H from 4 to 10. This suggested the possibility of applying massive chromium as an indicator electrode in acid-base titrations (Tourky, Issa and Khalifa, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1954, 11, 563).

Electrodes of type B set up potentials which within the p_H range 3-8 exhibit considerable drifts to less positive values (curves d, e and f, Fig. 2) amounting to 200-300 mv. At p_H 9 to 12 the potentials tend slightly to more positive values. The p_H -potential plot

for the potentials set three hours after immersion (curve d, Fig. 3) manifests more regular variation throughout the whole p_H range. In presence of chloride ions the potentials set are also less positive as in case of electrodes of type A.

FIG. 3

Electrodes of type C set up potentials which on immersion lie on the negative side of the hydrogen electrode slope (curve a, Fig. 3) but tend in general to assume less negative values with time (curve a'-f, Fig. 2). However, at p_H 8-12 an initial decrease in potential is observed which becomes more pronounced at higher p_H values before the subsequent drifts to less negative potentials. Such electrodes after being anodically polarised exhibit initial drifts in potential to less positive values at p_H 3 to 10 which become also more pronounced with rise of p_H .

This behaviour is apparently due to the presence, within the electrodeposited chromium of occluded hydrogen, which on diffusing away reduces portions of the passivating film and leads to less negative potentials. On anodic polarisation the surface is oxidised, but the potential tends at first to assume less positive values when the oxidation product is removed through hydrogen diffusing towards the electrode surface, before tending again to become less negative.

Behaviour of Chromium Electrodes out of contact with Air

The potentials set by electrodes of type A in oxygen-free buffers after heating in hydrogen at 1000° and subjecting them to high vacuum at this temperature, manifest slight variation with time to more positive values during three hours after immersion (curves s_1, s_2, s_3 , Fig. 4). The potentials lie always on the negative side of the hydrogen electrode slope (curve III, Fig. 5). After prolonged immersion considerable drifts to less negative values are observed (Fig. 4).

Electrodes of type B, subjected only to high vacuum at 1000°, set potentials which remain practically constant (curves P_1, P_2, P_3 , Fig. 4) throughout a period of 24 hours, and which lie again on the negative side of the hydrogen electrode slope (curve III, Fig. 5). The same behaviour manifests itself when the electrodes are subjected to the alternate action of hydrogen and high vacuum at the same temperature, except for the fact that the potentials are somewhat more negative (curve IV, Fig. 5).

Electrodes of type C subjected only to high vacuum at 400° set potentials which show continuous drifts to less negative values (curves E_1, E_2, E_3 , Fig. 4) and lie very close to the hydrogen electrode slope (curve II, Fig. 5).

FIG. 4

(S, P and E same as in Fig. 2).

FIG. 5

With all types of electrodes the potentials show more linearity with p_H than in aerated solutions.

For the sake of comparison, the E_0' values obtained by extrapolating the linear portions of the $E_h - p_H$ plots, obtained both in air (Fig. 3) and out of its contact (Fig. 5), by plotting the potentials set 3 hours after immersion against p_H to $p_H = 0$, together with the thermodynamic E_0' value of the Cr/Cr₂O₃ system are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
[E_0' in millivolts].

Electrodes.	In aerated solution.	Out of contact with air.	Thermodynamic.
Type A	+ 450	- 70	- 570
Type B	+ 480	- 70 or - 100	- 570
Type C	- 30	- 30	- 570

However, it is noteworthy to remark that on exposing the treated electrodes to air considerable shifts to more positive values are observed due to the redevelopment of the passivating films on chromium.

It is probable that the oxide, which forms on chromium and to which is attributed the passivity of the metal, is the trioxide. If the formation of the oxide takes place according to the reaction:

hence, from a knowledge of the free energy of formation of each of the reactants and products, the net free energy change of the reaction and accordingly the reversible potential of the Cr/Cr₂O₃ system can be computed. The free energy of formation of Cr₂O₃ at 25°, as calculated from the relation $\Delta F = \Delta H - T \Delta S$, is -24680 cal. For calculating the latter value, ΔS values at 298.1 for O₂, Cr₂O₃ and elementary Cr of 49.003, 19.4 and 5.68 cal., and a ΔH value for Cr₂O₃ of -269700 cal. are used. Taking the free energy of water and OH⁻ ion at 25° equal to -56690 and -37595 cal. respectively, ΔF of the above reaction amounts to -186380 cal. from which the E_0' value of the Cr/Cr₂O₃ system is -0.57 v [$E_0(\text{OH}^- - \text{H}_2) = -0.828 \text{ V.}$] (Latimer "Oxidation Potentials", Prentice-Hall, N.Y., 1953; pp. 39, 246).

Comparison of the E_0' value of -0.57 v with the experimental ones obtained both in air and out of contact with atmospheric oxygen indicates that in no case we are able to approach the reversible potential of the Cr/Cr₂O₃ system. The values obtained in air are considerably more positive than those obtained after subjecting the electrodes to the alternate action of hydrogen and high vacuum at high temperatures, which in turn are less negative than the thermodynamic E_0' values.

The behaviour of the electrodes in aerated solutions can be explained by considering the metal to be covered by a pre-immersion oxide film which after immersion tends to become complete by precipitation inside its pores of corrosion products. Since chromic oxide is a higher-valent metal oxide, the lattice defects are most probably restricted to oxygen ions (Wagner, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1933, **B 21**, 25; 1936, **32**, 447; Wagner and Hammen, *ibid.*, 1938, **40**, 197). Diffusion of Cr³⁺ ions towards the oxide-solution interface is not liable to take place and the oxygen deposited on the electrode surface may persist as oxygen doublets, subjecting the electrodes to an oxygen overvoltage effect. Such electrodes behave as metal-metal oxide-oxygen rather than metal-metal oxide electrodes (Tourky and Mousa, *loc. cit.*). When the metal is subjected to the action of hydrogen, a large portion of this oxygen is removed and the electrode assumes less positive values. Based on the findings of Bowden (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1929, **A 125**, 420) the oxygen overvoltage effect, superimposing the reversible potential and amounting to one volt (in case of massive chromium), is sufficient to cover 2/3 of the electrode surface with oxygen doublets. Bowden (*loc. cit.*) found that the quantity of electricity necessary to establish oxygen overvoltage per 100 mv was 11×10^{-8} coulombs. As the real area in case of highly polished metal is 2-3 times the apparent one (Hickling, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1945, **41**, 333; Butler, "Electrical Phenomena at Interfaces", Methuen, London, p. 205, 1951), this latter quantity is sufficient to cover 1/15 of the surface with oxygen doublets.

In case of other metals, previously studied by Tourky *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), similar results were obtained and the higher potentials than the reversible ones were attributed to an oxygen overvoltage effect amounting to ~ 400, 200, 100 and 100 mv in case of molyb-

denum, tellurium antimony and arsenic electrodes, respectively. These potential increments correspond to $1/4$, $2/15$, $1/15$ and $1/15$ of the electrode surface being covered with oxygen doublets as compared with $2/3$ in the case of chromium. If the surface area of the electrode covered with oxygen doublets is taken as a measure of passivity, then those metals should be placed with respect to their passivity in the following order: Cr, Mo, Sb, As (Tourky, Issa and Khalifa, unpublished).

Further, when the electrodes are subjected to the action of hydrogen and to high vacuum, a good portion of the passivating film including metal oxide and oxygen doublets is removed whereby the potentials become more negative than those observed in aerated solutions.

The authors wish to express their thanks to Professor A. Riad Tourky for his valuable advice and criticism.

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Received December 8, 1955.

STUDIES IN THE PASSIVITY OF CHROMIUM. PART II. THE EFFECT OF ANIONS ON THE PASSIVATING FILM ON CHROMIUM

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From the study of the effect of anions on the passivity of chromium it is shown that the passivating action goes in the order: Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- . It is also shown that the potentials set in presence of oxygen are more positive than those set in presence of nitrogen. Similarly the potentials obtained in absence of chloride ions are more positive than in their presence.

In the previous investigation (this issue, p. 465) it has been shown that the passivity of chromium is due to the presence on the metal surface of an oxide film overlaid by an oxygen film which covers only $2/3$ of the area of the oxide surface. Müller (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1931, 37, 328; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, A68, 159) studied the effect of different acids on the activation of passive chromium and found it to depend upon the permeabilities of the different anions through the pores of the passivating film. The acid anions offered a frictional resistance both to the emergence of the metal ions from the lattice and to the entrance of hydrogen ions into the double layer. This was concluded from the fact that the liberation of hydrogen from acids by active chromium was greater, the smaller the radius of the acid anion. Further evidence as to the effect of anions can be gained from a study of the electrodic behaviour of massive chromium (which is easily passivated) during the initial build up of the electrode potential when present in solution containing them, under a variety of conditions.